

State Name: BIHAR
Third Reintroduction of Farmer's Varieties
2022-2023

PART-2
RABI SEASON

Fig.: Harvesting of Black Mustard Native Variety; Passbook Number – 811303-01-0064

GERMINATION REPORT, PLANT STANDING REPORT AND HARVESTING REPORT

To
FAO, ITPGRFA IV CYCLE PROJECT

BY
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Under the project
Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population

Seed Biodiversity Report:

Time Period for Sowing: November/December 2022

Note:

* 100 gm sample must be sent in PAIRVI office with the variety's name and crop name

* Each month report must be sent/parceled in PAIRVI office with sample plant/crop.

Reporting per month for:

- Reintroduction: 10 Trial plots

Responsible person for per month Reporting:

Seed Biodiversity:

Crop name	Variety name	Seed in CSB (for sowing)	New seed improved	Passbook no. (seed distribution)	Passbook no. For Reporting Under trial
LOTNI	Jasidih+ Madhopur	7kg		80,81,83,85, 86,12,18.	64
Black Mustard	Hareram Yadav	4.5kg		001,90,91,92, 93,	64
Black Mustard	Pusa bold	9kg	4kg	0033,34,35, 36,37,38,40	001
Yellow Mustard	Jasidih haat	12kg	4kg	005,007,008, 0012,0013, 0014,0018	001
Yellow Mustard	Bhuto ydav	7kg		24,23,22,23, 35,36,39,	0064
Chana	GNG	3kg		001,	0064
Chana	Jasidih Madhopur Basukitar	11kg		0015,0016, 065,041,042, 044.045,046	001
Chana	Khoripanan	2kg		56,	0085
Masoor	DL406	6kg		001,66,0068	087
Masoor	Madhopur Jasidih Bhuto.yadav	14kg		001,058,56, 55.0046	76
Matar (Pea)	P10	4.5kg	2kg	001,0069,070	79
Barley	Chakai	4kg		001,096	0064
Barley	Jyoti	2kg		90,	65
	Total	86 KG	6 KG		

Total Seed in circulation 92 Kg. for Rabi 2022-23 Season.

Germination report:

Farmer's Field Trial (Ms. Pudi Soren; 811303-01-0064)

Passbook No.	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing date	Date of Germination 50%	Any pest attack	Water logging	Other vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestions
Trial-1 811303-01-0064	Lotni	Jasidih+madhopur	18/11/2022	28/11/2022	NO	NO	NO	YES/
Trial-2 0064	black musted	hareram yadav	18/11/2022	29/11/2022	“	“	“	
Trial-3 0064	yellow musted	bhuto yadav	18/11/2022	28/11/2022	“	“	“	
Trial-4 0064	chana	gng	18/11/2022	29/11/2022	“	“	“	
Trial-5 0064	barley	chakai	20/11/2022	29/11/2022	“	“	“	

Image Trial _1 Germination

Image Trial _3 Germination

Farmer's Field Trial (Hareram Yadav; 811303-01-0001)

Passbook No.	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing date	Date of Germination 50%	Any pest attack	Water logging	Other vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestions
Trial-1 001	black musted	pusa bold	15/11/2022	24/11/2022	No	No	No	yes
Trial-2 001	yellow musted	jasidih haat	15/11/2022	23/11/2022	“	“	“	
Trial-3 001	chana	jasidih madhopu basukitar haat	17/11/2022	28/11/2022	“	“	“	

Image Trial _3 Germination **chana**

Image Trial _2 Germination **yellow mused**

Image Trial _1 Germination **black mused**

Farmer's Field Trial (811303-01-0085, 0087,0076,0079,0065)

Passbook No.	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing date	Date of Germination 50%	Any pest attack	Water logging	Other vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestions
0085	Chana	khoripana n	19/11/2022	29/11/2022	N0	No	No	yes
0087	Masoor	dl406	22/11/2022	30/11/2022	‘	‘	‘	‘
0076	Masoor	madhopur jasidih bhuto yadav	20/11/2022	30/11/2022	‘	‘	‘	‘
0079	Pea	p10	18/11/2022	29/11/2022	‘	‘	‘	‘
0065	Barley	jyoti	22/11/2022	30/11/2022	‘	‘	‘	‘

Ac no 0079 image matar

ac no 0085 image chana

Ac no 0076 image masoor

ac no 0065 image barle

Ac no 0087 image masoor

Standing Crop Report:

Farmer's Field Trial (Ms. Pudi Soren; 811303-01-0064)

Reporting Date 31/01/2023

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variet Y	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any diseas observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist (y/N) Y Date required for scientist	Other vulnerable factor
FARM.1	Lotni	70%	40%	No	No	Yes	No
Farm.2	Black musted	60%	25%	No	No	“	“
Farm.3	Yrllow.musted	75%	35%	No	No	“	“
Farm.4	Chana	70%	8%	No	No	“	“
Farm.5	beary	80%	10%	No	No	“	“

Farm no 3 image yello w musted

farm no 5 image Barley

farm no 4 image chana

farm 2 image black mustered		farm no 1 image lotni

Farmer's Field Trial ((811303-01-0085, 0087,0076,0079,0065))

Reporting Date 31/01/2023

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
0085	chana/khoripanna	75%	5%	No	No	Yes	No
0087	Masoor dl406/	80%	25%	No	No	“	“
0076	masoor/madhopur/jasidih/bhuto	75%	20%	no	no	“	“
0079	mater /p10	65%	25%	no	no	“	“
0065	barley/jayoti	85%	0%	no	“	“	“

A/c no 0079 image Mater (Pea)	A/c no 0087 image Masoor	A/c no 0076 image Masoor

A/c no 0085 image Chana	A/c no 0065 image Barley	
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Farmer's Field Trial (Hareram Yadav; 811303-01-0001)

Reporting Date 31/01/2023

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety Y	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist (y/N) Y Date required for scientist	Another vulnerable factor
Trial 1	Black musted	75%	35%	No	No	Yes	No
Trial 2	Yellow musted	65%	45%	No	No	“	“
Trial 3	chana	55%	5%	no	no	“	“

Farm no 1 black musted	Farm no 1 black musted	farm no 3 image chana
Farm no 2 yellow musted		

Harvesting Report:

Report
Pod and Harvesting
Reporting 23/03/2023

BIHAR

Sowing Month: Oct/November 2022

Trial Plot at Farmer's Field at Passbook No. 85,87,76,79,65

Trail plot no/passbook no.-	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
0085	Chana Khoripanna	8/2/2023	1-2	30-50	No	24/3/2023	5kg	Gerua	No
0087	Masoor DL406	9/2/2023	1-2	35-55	Yes, flower, drop	20/3/2023	8kgkg	Bhura	No
0076	Masoor Madhopur jasidih, bhuto yadaw	12/2/2023	1-2	30-60	Flower drop	21/3/2023	10kg	Bhura	No
0079	Pea; P 10	11/2/2023	4-6	20-35	No	19/3/2023	8kg	White	No
0065	Barley/jyoti	16/2/2023	25-40	4-8	no	24/3/2023	12kg	golden	no

- Sequence of trial plot no. for best grow;
From Best growth... 0076,0087,0065,0079,005 to Slow growth
- Trial farm with seme/equal farer varieties;
Group
A.1) 005 Chana
B.1) 0076 and 0087 Masoor
C.1) 0079 and 0065 Pea

Identified characteristics:

Crop name	(Seed size, seed color. Plant size and color, Branches, Hairy stem or leaves and others, Flowering time)
0085	Seed size
0087	Seed size
0076	Hairy stem or leaves and others flowers
0079	Plants size, colour
0065	Seed size colour

Ac no0085 image chana

ac no 0079 image mater

ac no 0087 image masoor

Ac no0076 image masoor

ac no 0065 image bearly

Trial Plot at Farmer's Field (Hareram Yadav; 811303-0001)

Trail plot no/passbook no.811303-0001	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plants	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
Trial 1 811303-0001	Black musted, pusa bold	3/2/2023	10-15	40-50	No	22/3/2023	6kg	White 10-15	No
Trial 2 811303-0001	Yellow musted, jasi dihaat	30/1/2023	20-35	35-45	No	20/3/2023	5kg	Red/white 35-45	No
Trial 3 811303-0001	Chana, jasi dihaat, basukit ar, haat madhopur	15/2/2023	1-2	20-30	no	20/2/2023	4kg	White 1-2	No

Yellow Mustard

farm no 2 black musted

farm no 3 image chana

Trial Plot at Farmer's Field (Pudi Soren; 0064)

Trail plot no/passbook no.- 0064	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
Trial 1 0064	Lotni, madhopur, Jasidih	5/2/2023	4-6	40-50	No	18/3/2023	5kg	Black	No
Trial 2 0064	Black musred, hareram yadav	8/2/2023	8-12	35-60	“	23/2023	6kg	Black	“
Trial 3 0064	Yellow musted, bhuto yadav	5/2/2023	10-25	45-60	“	20/3/2023	5kg	Yellow	“
Trial 4 0064	Chana, Gng	20/2/2023	1-2	30-50	“	22/3/2023	4kg	Bhura	“
Trial 5 0064	Barley chakai	24/2/2023	25-40	4-8	“	25/3/2023	8kg	white	“

Farm 2 image black musted

farm no 1 image lotni

farm no 3 image yellow musted

Farm no 4 image chana

farm no 5 image barley
